

**INVENTIO, DISPOSITIO Y ELOCUTIO
EN LA OBRA “LA STEAUA” DE MIHAI EMINESCU
Y SU TRADUCCIÓN EN ESPAÑOL DE VICENTE APARICIO /**

**INVENTIO, DISPOSITIO AND ELOCUTIO
IN MIHAI EMINESCU'S “LA STEAUA” AND ITS TRANSLATION
IN SPANISH BY VICENTE APARICIO**

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Received: June 1, 2025 | Reviewed: June 3, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

We propose a detailed investigation of Vicente Aparicio’s Spanish translation of Mihai Eminescu’s poem “La steaua”. Our analysis adopts a dual theoretical perspective: on the one hand, we examine the poem’s deep structure and organization through the rhetorical notions of invention and disposition; on the other hand, we also focus on its surface structure, namely elocution. This approach allows us to explore both the mechanisms of meaning construction and the stylistic aspect of the translated version. Additionally, we employ a comparative-contrastive perspective to highlight the specific challenges posed by the process of translation.